

Power Scaling and Thermo-Optics of Ho:KY(WO₄)₂ Thin-Disk Lasers: Effect of Ho³⁺ Concentration

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October, 2nd 2017. **AM3A.3**

ASSL 2017, Nagoya, JAPAN

OUTLINE

*Motivation and introduction. The **monoclinic double tungstates***

*Fabrication of the **thin-disk** structures*

*Spectroscopy of the **Ho** ions*

*Laser setup for the **Ho thin-disk** laser*

Achieved results

Conclusion and future work

MOTIVATION

State of the art. Tm –based thin-disk lasers

500 μm thick, 10 at.% Tm:YAG: up to 2 W ($T = -30^\circ \text{C}$), *A. Dienes et al., CLEO'98.*

650 μm thick, 6 at.% Tm:YAG: up to 4 W ($T = -17^\circ \text{C}$), *N. Berner et al., ASSL'99.*

- 4 bounces of the pump(8 pump passes)

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200-500 μm thick, 5 at.% Tm:Lu₂O₃: 0.5 W, *M. Schellhorn et al., ASSP, ATuB14 (2011).*

- 12 bounces of the pump

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250 μm thick, 12 at.% Tm:LLF: 21 W @1910 nm *G. Stoepler et al., Opt. Lett. 37, 1163 (2012).*

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Very complex pump scheme

MOTIVATION

State of the art. Ho –based thin-disk lasers

400 μm , 2 at.% Ho:YAG: 9.4 W @2090 nm, slope efficiency η of ~50% *M. Schellhorn, Appl. Phys. B85, 549 (2006)*

- 12 bounces of the pump (typical for YAG thin-disks), Ho-concentration limited because of upconversion losses
- pumped by a Tm:YLF laser

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400 μm , 2 at.% Ho:YAG: 15 W @2090 nm *J. Speiser et al., SPIE 7912, 79120C (2011)* and *Proc. of SPIE 8547, 85470E-1-11 (2012)*.

- 12 bounces of the pump, Ho-concentration limited because of upconversion losses.
- pumped by a Tm: fiber laser

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Even higher output power, 22 W with η ~27% was achieved in a similar mutipass-pumped Ho:YAG laser using an InP diode. *G. Renz, Proc. of SPIE 9342, 93421W (2015)*.

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GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Our aim was to develop a **Ho thin-disk** laser with
simplified pump geometry based on the **monoclinic**
double tungstate crystals

INTRODUCTION

Monoclinic double tungstates

Substituted ions:
 Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Lu^{3+}

Trivalent active ions:
 Yb^{3+} , Tm^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Ho^{3+}

Structural and thermal properties

High doping levels for the active ions

Moderate thermal conductivity

"Athermal" thermo-optic behaviour

example: *KLuW* crystal

Ln^{3+} spectroscopic properties

Large transition cross-sections

Broad absorption and emission bands

Weak concentration-quenching

Strong Raman activity

V. Petrov, et al., Laser Photonics Rev. 1, 179 (2007).

INTRODUCTION

- ⇒ Ideal suited for the thin disk laser concept
- ⇒ Disk thickness $<100\ \mu\text{m}$ sufficient absorption.
- ⇒ Epitaxial structures required
- ⇒ Single bounce pumping possible: Typically ~ 12 bounces of the pump (24 pump passes).
- ⇒ Reduced complexity of the pump geometry

Thin-Disk laser based on $50\ \mu\text{m}$ $\text{Yb}(32\%):\text{KLuW}$ epitaxy

S. Rivier et al., Opt. Lett. 33, 735 (2008).

INTRODUCTION

Thin-Disk laser based on 250 μm Tm(5%):KLuW epitaxy

S. Vatik et al., *Opt. Lett.* 37, 356 (2012).

Output coupler:
 $T_{OC} = 4\%$, $R_{OC} = -40$ mm.

Pump laser light: horizontally polarized, $E // N_m$

October, 2nd 2017. **AM3A.3**

ASSL 2017, Nagoya, JAPAN

FABRICATION of the THIN DISK STRUCTURES

MDT substrates.

Top-Seeded Solution Growth (TSSG) method.
Oriented normal to the *b*-axis.
They are 1 – 1.5 mm-thick.

Epitaxies.

Liquid Phase Epitaxy (LPE) method

FABRICATION of the THIN DISK STRUCTURES

SPECTROSCOPY of Ho^{3+} in MDT CRYSTALS

Larger gain for $E // N_m$

Absorption and emission cross-section of **Ho:KYW**. $5I_7 \leftrightarrow 5I_8$ transition near 2000 nm. Light polarization $E // N_m$

LASER SETUP for the **Ho:KYW THIN-DISK**

The **pump source** was a Tm fiber laser (model IFL15, LISA laser products, OHG) emitting up to 12.5 W at 1960 nm (FWHM = 1.5 nm, unpolarized output with $M^2 \sim 1$).

Active layer
3 or 5at.% **Ho:KYW**
 $250 \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$

LASER RESULTS – quasi-CW mode

The 3 at. % Ho:KYW laser generated a peak power of **1.10 W** at 2056-2059 nm and η of **66%**

The 5 at. % Ho:KYW laser provided an increased output power of **1.31 W** (higher absorption) at 2057-2059 and 2072-2075 nm albeit at reduced slope efficiency, $\eta = 34\%$.

Pump absorption, single bounce:

3at.% Ho, Abs = 14%, **5at.% Ho**, Abs = 33%

Stronger thermo-optic aberrations and higher upconversion losses associated with stronger heat load at higher **Ho³⁺** doping.

Neither fracture of the disk nor thermal roll-over of the output dependence were observed up to at least $P_{\text{abs}} = 4.20$ W.

LASER RESULTS – CW mode

Agreement with the gain spectra.

In the CW mode, the difference in the output performance was more pronounced:

The 3 at. % Ho:KYW laser generated **1.01 W** with $\eta = 60\%$ whereas the maximum output from the 5 at. % Ho:KYW laser was only **0.24 W** with $\eta = 15\%$.

The effect of **Ho³⁺** concentration is due to the increasing reabsorption losses.

LASER RESULTS – thermo-optic effects

CW
3at.%Ho:KYW

CW
5at.%Ho:KYW

X'_1 and X'_3 – principal axes of the thermal expansion tensor of **KYW**.

For the 3 at. % Ho:KYW laser, beam ellipticity: $e = 0.64$, $M^2_x = 3.0$ and $M^2_y = 1.6$),

For the 5 at. % Ho:KYW laser, the beam confined and became extended along the vertical direction y ($e = 0.60$ and $M^2_x = 1.4$, $M^2_y = 1.5$).

LASER RESULTS – thermo-optic effects

Modelling of the distortions (ray transfer matrix formalism)

For the 3 at. % **Ho:KYW** thin-disk laser,

Pure negative (defocusing) lens

Sensitivity factors ($M = dD/dP_{abs}$) of $M_x = -1.7$, $M_y = -0.7$ m⁻¹/W.

Related to the negative thermo-optic coefficient of **KYW** at $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$, $dn_m/dT = -8.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and to the suppression of the positive impact of end-bulging by the substrate acting as an undoped cap.

In contrast, the 5 at. % Ho-doped thin-disk shows positive thermal lens with $M_x = 5.2$, $M_y = 0.5$ m⁻¹/W. This leads to the cavity instability for the 5 at.% Ho:KYW laser in CW and the same effect prevented laser operation of the 7 and 10 at. % Ho:KYW thin disks.

LASER RESULTS – thermo-optic effects

Measurement of the upconversion luminescence. For low (**3 at. % Ho**) doping: Dominant emission from 5I_5 (at ~913 nm), populated by the phonon-assisted energy-transfer upconversion process ETU1.

For higher Ho doping: Dominant emissions from higher-lying $^5S_2+^5F_4$ (at ~545 nm) and 5F_5 states (at ~660 nm), populated through different ETU and cross-relaxation processes whose efficiency is enhanced with the **Ho** doping level.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Successful operation of **Ho:KYW** thin-disk lasers based on the LPE technology delivering >1 W at ~ 2056 or ~ 2073 nm with a slope efficiency $\sim 60\%$ using a simple single bounce pump geometry.

Role of the **Ho³⁺** concentration on the output characteristics of such lasers (slope efficiency, beam profile and emission wavelength). Increasing thermo-optic distortions with doping caused by the disk bulging and strong interaction of the **Ho³⁺** ions leading to upconversion losses.

Power scaling of **Ho:KYW** thin-disk lasers by optimizing the **Ho³⁺** doping (1-3 at. %), multi-pass pumping, or alteration of the laser element orientation (e.g., for light propagation along the N_g -axis).

Thank you for your attention

This work was supported by:

The Spanish Government: Projects MAT2016-75716-C2-1-R, (AEI/FEDER,UE), MAT2013-47395-C4-4-R and TEC2014-55948-R.

The Generalitat de Catalunya: Project 2014SGR1358.

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 657630.

Francesc Díaz acknowledges additional support through the ICREA academia award 2010ICREA-02 for excellence in research.

Pavel Loiko acknowledges support from the Government of the Russian Federation (Grant 074-U01) through ITMO Post-Doctoral Fellowship scheme.

October, 2nd 2017. **AM3A.3**

ASSL 2017, Nagoya, JAPAN